

Replacing Phonetic Squiggles? A New Diacritic System for Encoding English Pronunciation Preserving Standard Orthography

Zbigniew Stachowicz, Independent researcher,

e-mail: zrstachowicz@gmail.com , ORCID: 0000-0003-2272-1514

First published: June 30, 2025; last updated: October 29, 2025

Abstract

This article introduces a novel diacritic-based system for encoding English pronunciation for educational purposes, without altering standard orthography. By using diacritical marks, the system maintains full compliance with standard spelling while representing pronunciation with a level of precision comparable to IPA phonemic notation, making it particularly well-suited for independent learners. This dual-function notation guides articulation while reinforcing spelling patterns, making it a practical tool for self-study materials and pedagogical texts. The article demonstrates that such a system is feasible, relatively straightforward, and although a few exceptions exist, it handles even highly irregular English words with considerable accuracy. A Word template facilitating the typing of diacritics and IPA symbols is attached to the article.

1. Introduction – Purpose and Concept

The spelling of English, unlike that of most other languages written in the Latin alphabet, is characterized by the absence of diacritical marks and consistent rules linking spelling to pronunciation. Dictionaries commonly use a complex system of IPA-based pronunciation symbols, requiring learners to master spelling and pronunciation separately. As a result, many students struggle with correct spelling or articulation, depending on whether they rely more on visual or auditory memory.

This article presents a new method for indicating the pronunciation of English words using diacritical marks placed directly on the standard spelling. The core principle of this approach is that standard orthography remains unchanged once the diacritical marks are removed. Surprisingly, this proves both feasible and relatively straightforward. The proposed diacritic-based notation is designed to match the precision of IPA phonemic notation, suitable for learners with minimal simplifications or exceptions. The notation can be useful in learning English as a foreign language, especially for older students or those learning independently. It is particularly suitable for self-study tutorials.

In the past, attempts to reform English orthography or introduce diacritical marks to indicate pronunciation, such as those in Webster's dictionaries and the Initial Teaching Alphabet, either failed to preserve standard orthography or only approximated pronunciation. As a non-native speaker, I created this notation to make English pronunciation more accessible to learners like me. The diacritical marks adopted differ from those in previous systems, such as Merriam-Webster, as they proved less intuitive for learners. I have adopted those that I believe will be more intuitive for students familiar with diacritical marks used in other European languages, ensuring they do not suggest incorrect pronunciation.

2. Background

Spelling and pronunciation in other languages

Most languages written in the Latin alphabet, such as French, German, Spanish, and my native Polish, use spelling systems that, despite complexity, reflect the pronunciation quite accurately. Although a single sound may vary in spelling across words, consistent orthographic rules and diacritical marks ensure generally predictable pronunciation with few exceptions. As a result, dictionaries for these languages rarely require phonetic notation. English is an exception. Its spelling bears little relation to pronunciation, posing minimal issues for native speakers, who learn pronunciation through daily exposure, but presenting significant difficulties for non-native learners.

In languages like Arabic or Hebrew, which use abjads (consonantal alphabets), the spelling, as in English, does not reflect pronunciation. Although diacritical marks are not used in everyday writing, these languages have complex diacritic systems to indicate pronunciation. These notations do not alter the standard orthography and are applied in special contexts like education, dictionaries, proper names, religion, and poetry, where diacritics are sometimes added for clarity.

Given English's role as the world's primary lingua franca, this raises a question: could introducing diacritical marks into English spelling without changing existing orthography enable unambiguous pronunciation, as seen in other languages? This article argues that, contrary to appearances, the answer is affirmative. However, due to the lack of a unified standard pronunciation in English, this diacritical notation system is primarily suited for language learning aid rather than for broader application.

IPA transcription systems for representing pronunciation in English dictionaries

In English dictionaries, pronunciation is most commonly represented by simplified IPA phonemic transcription. Unlike phonetic transcription (written in square brackets []), phonemic transcription (in slashes //) omits allophonic variations, namely sounds that realize a phoneme in specific contexts without changing word meaning.

Different dictionaries adopt slightly varying conventions for IPA phonemic transcription. For example, some dictionaries use /e/ while others use /ɛ/ for the same phoneme. Similarly, some use /i/, others /ɪ/, or both (e.g., /ɪ/ and /i/) to reflect pronunciation differences, even if they are not always distinct phonemes.

Dialects of English pronunciation

English, a global language, has diverse pronunciation variants across different countries. Non-English-speaking students are typically taught one of two standard pronunciation variants: British Received Pronunciation (RP) or General American (GA). Both varieties use standard IPA phoneme sets, differing mainly in vowels (see Table 1). One of the most significant differences is that RP is a non-rhotic dialect, while GA is rhotic. In GA, the /r/ sound is always audible, whereas in RP, /r/ is pronounced only before a vowel or in linking /r/ contexts (e.g., „car” vs. „car and”).

Table 1.

The phoneme sets in RP and GA

Consonants	RP, GA	/b/, /d/, /dʒ/, /f/, /g/, /h/, /j/, /l/, /m/, /n/, /ŋ/, /p/, /k/, /r/, /s/, /ʃ/, /tʃ/, /t/, /θ/, /ð/, /v/, /w/, /z/, /ʒ/
Vowels	RP	/æ/, /ɑ:/, /ʌ/, /e/, /ə/, /ɜ:/, /ɪ/, /i:/, /ɒ/, /ɔ:/, /ʊ/, /u:/
	GA	/æ/, /ɑ/, /ʌ/, /e/, /ə/, /ɚ/, /ɜ/, /ɪ/, /i/, /ɔ/, /ʊ/, /u/
Diphthongs (and glides)	RP	/eɪ/, /aɪ/, /ɔɪ/, /əʊ/, /aʊ/, (/ju:/)
	GA	/eɪ/, /aɪ/, /ɔɪ/, /oʊ/, /aʊ/, (/ju/)

In most cases, the phonemes used in RP and GA are either identical or have direct equivalents, such as /ɑː/-/ɑ/, /ɔː/-/ɔ/ or /əʊ/-/oʊ/. As a result, the proposed diacritical system is suitable for both dialects and uses the same characters to denote equivalent phonemes. Thus, differences in the application of the system for the two dialects are not very significant and primarily lie in the phonemic value of certain symbols and the way they are used in some words.

This article focuses primarily on the application of the diacritic system to the British variant (RP), using the Cambridge Dictionary as its reference source for phonemic transcription.

3. Description of the Proposed Phonemic Notation System

The diacritical notation system was developed with the intention of completely replacing the IPA system in the scope of standard phonemes used in English. This goal has been almost entirely achieved. Of course, the characters in this system don't correspond exactly to IPA symbols. The assumption that the standard orthography must remain unchanged means that the same phoneme must often be represented by several different characters. In several cases, the same character can correspond to different phonemes depending on the context, but this follows clear and simple rules.

There are few exceptions that cannot be written using the proposed range of characters. For such cases, it would be necessary to introduce additional characters, which would complicate the system, or to record the pronunciation in an approximate way, or traditionally, e.g. using IPA characters. However, these are very few exceptions.

3.1 Proposed Diacritical Symbols and Characters

In this article, the terms 'diacritic symbol', 'mark' or 'diacritic', refer to a modifying mark (e.g., ´, ¨), while a 'character' denotes a letter combined with a diacritic (e.g., ś, ô, ů).

The diacritic symbols are designed to be intuitive for students familiar with diacritical marks used in other European languages, and in particular, to avoid suggesting incorrect pronunciation. In the presented proposal, the most important diacritics denote:

- horizontal line above the letters – mute letters,
- underline under vowels – syllable stress, under consonants – voiced pronunciation,
- acute accent (´) over consonants – postalveolar sibilants (/ʃ/, /ʒ/),
- acute accent (´) over vowels – typically long pronounced monophthongs,
- caron (ˇ) over vowels – diphthongs, over consonants* - affricates (/tʃ/, /dʒ/),
- grave accent (`) over vowels – reduced pronunciation (/ə/, /ɜː/),
- circumflex (^ resembling A) above vowel – pronunciation as /ʌ/ or similar as /a/,
- dot above (resembling dot over i) – pronunciation as /ɪ/ or similar as /i/,
- ring above (° resembling O) – pronunciation similar to /ɔː/ /ɔ/ or similar,
- breve (˘ resembling U) – pronunciation as /uː/, /u/, or similar.

* The caron (ˇ) in d' and t' is typically rendered by word processors, such as Microsoft Word, as an apostrophe-like character.

The choice of symbols is arbitrary, and changes may be discussed during the development of the system. Alternatively, a dot under the letter could mark mute letters, while for diphthongs, e.g., a horizontal line, tilde, or umlaut instead of caron could be used.

All proposed diacritical marks, their description and phonemic value of the characters (i.e. letters with diacritical marks) are presented in Table 2.

Table 2.

Diacritical marks with a description and phonemic value of the characters

Description of the Marks	Meaning	Characters with the Marks, Comments
Marks used for all letters		
Horizontal line above the letter	Mute	ā, b̄(b), c̄, d̄(d), ē, f̄, ḡ, h̄(h), ī, j̄, k̄(k), l̄(l), m̄, n̄, ō, p̄, q̄, r̄, s̄, t̄, ū, w̄, x̄, ȳ, z̄
Underline	Under vowels – syllable stress	a, ai, eu etc.
	under consonants - voiced pronunciation	z - /z/, th - /ð/, x - /gz/
Marks for consonant letters		
Consonants without marks	According to general rules	The rules are described later in the article
Acute accent (´) above consonants: ć, ǵ, ś, ʦ, ʧ, ʤ	Postalveolar sibilants (hushing consonants)	ś, ć, ʧ, ʦ - /ʃ/, ǵ, ʤ, ǰ - /ʒ/ ʧ - /kʃ/
Caron (ˇ)	Affricates	ǧ - /dʒ/, ǰ - /dʒ/, ʦ - /tʃ/
Grave accent (`) in ÿ (non-rhotic as RP only)	Schwa /ə/ or /ær/ if before audible vowel	in sequences e.g.: eÿ - /eə/ or /eær/ uÿ - /ʊə/ or /ʊær/
Marks for letters-vowels		
No marks	Basic short vowels	a - /æ/ e - /e/, /ɛ/ i, y - /ɪ/, (/i/) o - /ɒ/(RP), /ɑ/(GA) u - /ʊ/
Acute accent (´) above vowels: á, é, í, ý, ó, ú:	Typically long pronounced monophthongs (clear vowels)	á - /ɑ:/(RP), /ɑ/(GA) é, í, ý - /i:/(RP), /i/(GA) ó - /ɔ:/(RP), /ɔ/(GA) ú - /u:/(RP), /u/(GA)
Caron (ˇ) or háček above vowels ǎ, ě, ě, ǚ, ǔ, ǖ	Diphthongs or glides	ǎ, ě - /eɪ/ ǚ, ǚ - /aɪ/ ǔ - /əʊ/(RP), /oʊ/(GA) ǖ - /ju:/(RP), /ju/(GA)
Grave accent (`) above vowels	Reduced vowels: schwa /ə/ if unstressed or /ɜ:/, /ɛ:/ if stressed	à, è, ì, ÿ, ò, ù - /ə/ if stressed (usually before r): èr, ìr, ÿr, òr, ùr - /ɜ:/(RP) èr, ìr, ÿr, òr, ùr - /ɛ:/ (GA)
Dot above vowels (resembling dot over i): ä, ê, ô, ù	Pronounced as /ɪ/	â, è, ò, ù - /ɪ/
Circumflex (^ resembling A) over ô, û	Pronounced as /ʌ/ (or similar)	ô, û - /ʌ/ in sequences: ôu, ôw - /aʊ/
Ring above (° resembling O)	pronounced as /ɔ: / /ɔ/ (or similar)	å - /ɔ:/(RP), /ɔ/(GA) ũ - /ɔ:/(RP), êw - /oʊ/(GA),
Breve (˘ resembling U)	Pronounced as /u: /, /u/ (or similar)	ö - /u:/(RP), /u/(GA), ëw - /u: /
Other		ä - /e/ â - /ɒ/ (RP) ô - /ʊ/ ù - /jə/ (reduced ũ)

As presented in Table 2, some characters have slightly different phonemic values depending on whether they indicate British (RP) or American (GA) pronunciation; for example, the character *ö* is pronounced as /əʊ/ in RP or /oʊ/ in GA.

As can be seen, the system contains a large number of diacritical marks and characters that are not easy to type in commonly used text editors such as Word. Therefore, a template file (*Diacritics.dotm*) has been included with this article, containing macros and keyboard shortcuts that make this task much easier. A brief guide will be displayed within the document when the file is opened.

3.2 Applying the Proposed Phonemic Transcription

The core assumption is that standard spelling remains unchanged after omitting the proposed diacritical marks. To meet this requirement, pronunciation is derived from combining these marks, their specific rules of application and interpretation, and existing English spelling conventions.

The description below outlines how to notate the phonemic values of individual sounds while maintaining standard spelling, focusing on British pronunciation (RP).

3.2.1. Rules and Notes about Consonants

1) When diacritical marks are not used, the general pronunciation rules for consonants apply, of which the following deserve special attention:

- Letter 'c' before 'e', 'i', or 'y' is pronounced as /s/, otherwise as /k/.
- The digraph 'ch' is pronounced as /tʃ/, other pronunciations are indicated with diacritical marks.
- The digraph 'gh' is pronounced as /g/ at the beginning of a word and as /f/ in the middle or at the end, and is marked with appropriate diacritical signs if mute or pronounced differently.
- 'n' before /g/ or /k/, and the digraph 'ng' at the end of a syllable are pronounced as /ŋ/.
- Letter l(L) represents the phoneme /l/ which is pronounced as clear [l] before vowels, as dark [ɫ] elsewhere (e.g., love [lʌv], feel [fi:ɫ])

2) In cases where the consonants are mute or their pronunciation differs from the general rules, diacritical marks are used. Detailed rules for marking consonant pronunciation are presented in Table 3.

3) The consonants s', 'th', 'x' are usually voiceless (/s/, /θ/, /ks/), but when voiced (/z/, /ð/, /gz/ - typically between vowels) are marked with an underline, e.g. mōthèr, fáthèr, éāsy, búsy, Wednēsdäy, èxact.

4) -r or -re at the end of a word is usually mute (in RP), unless the next word begins with a vowel, then the final -r is pronounced (the so-called linking r). Therefore, the endings '-r' and '-re' are not marked as mute.

5) Marking mute consonants is optional in the following cases:

- k in kn- at the beginning of a word is always mute, so marking \bar{k} is optional.
- 'r' before consonant, which is mute in RP.

6) Although the characters 't' and 't' are visually similar, 't' (with an acute accent, representing /j/) consistently occurs before 'i', whereas 't' (with a caron, representing /tʃ/) is always found before 'u'. Knowing this will help avoid mistakes.

Table 3.

Table of marking the pronunciation of consonants with diacritical marks.

Phone me IPA	c	ch	d	g	gh	j	ph	s	t	th	x	z	Comments
	Diacritic Notation of Pronunciation												
/s/	c *							s					* before e, i, y
/k/	c *	cĥ											*with exception as above
/z/								<u>s</u>			<u>x</u> *	z	* at the word beginning
/gz/											<u>x</u>		
/ʃ/	ć	ćh						sh, ś	ť *				*before i
/tʃ/		ch							ť *				*before u
/kʃ/											ć		
/ʒ/				ǰ				<u>ś</u>				ź	
/dʒ/			d'	ǰ		j							
/g/				g	gh*, gĥ								*at the word beginning
/f/					gh*		ph						*in the middle or at the end of a word
/t/								t	tĥ				
/θ/										th			
/ð/										<u>th</u>			

Remark: The pronunciation of consonants not given in the table is unambiguous or results from general rules and does not require marking with diacritics.

3.2.2. Rules and Notes about Vowels and Diphthongs

Detailed rules for writing the phonemic values of vowels and diphthongs are presented in Table 4. The general rules are as follows:

1) When diacritics are not provided, the letters a, e, i, y, o, u without signs are pronounced as /æ/, /e/, /ɪ/, /ɒ/, /ʊ/ respectively.

2) The phonemes /ə/, /ɜ:/ are written with the same diacritic. The rule is that [ə] occurs in unstressed syllables and /ɜ:/ in stressed ones. The rules for marking stressed syllables are described in point 7).

3) Letter -e at the end of a word is usually mute, so the mute sign can be omitted. This does not apply to short monosyllabic words such as the, be, etc., where the ending -e is usually pronounced as [ə], [i], [i:], which is denoted as è, è or é respectively.

4) In some words, the pronunciation of the schwa /ə/ may be optional, so we can mark it as mute (e.g. ā ē), but for clarity notation à, è, ì, ò, ù is preferred.

5) At the end of the word, the phoneme /ɪ/ (written e.g. by -y, -è) is pronounced as [i] instead of [ɪ] - so-called happy vowel.

6) The pronunciation of some letter sequences results from combining the phonemic values of the characters (i. e. letters with their diacritical marks). In some cases, the pronunciation can be written using diacritics in two or several ways, and for a few sequences their phonemic value differs slightly from the result of simply putting together the individual characters. In particular, the letter 'w' sometimes takes the value /ʊ/ or /u:/, and the characters denoting the phonemes /ɪ/ or /i:/ in some compounds take the value /j/. So for example, 'éw' means /ju:/. This is shown in detail in Table 4.

7) We omit marking the stress in monosyllabic words. In multisyllabic words, the stress usually falls on the penultimate syllable – so we can also omit marking the stress if this rule is followed. Exceptions to this rule should be marked by underlining the appropriate vowels.

Table 4.

Table of diacritical markings for vowels, diphthongs and specific phoneme sequences (RP pronunciation dialect - British English)

Phonemes (RP, IPA)	Characters							Character Sequences Representing Phonemes	Comments
	a	e	i	y	o	u	r		
	Diacritic notation of pronunciation								
/æ/	á								
/ɑ:/	á							ár, -ár	
/ʌ/					ô	û		ôû/ôû, ôô	
/e/	ä	e						äi, eä, iē	
/ə/	à	è	ì	ỳ	ò	ù		àr, èr, ìr, òr, ùr, -àr, -èr, -ìr, -òr, -ùr,	In an unstressed syllable
/ɜ:/		è	ì	ỳ	ò	ù		èr, èär, ìr, ùr, òr, ùr, -èr, -ìr, -òr, -ùr,	In a stressed syllable (usually before r)
/ɪ/	à	è	i	y	ò	ù		èè, èi, iē,	See rule 3)
/i:/		é	í	ý				éè/éé, éä, éi/éí, íé/iē	
/ɔ/	â				o			oû, oŵ	
/ɔ:/	â				ó	ú		óä, óó/óó, áw, áû, ár/-ár, úr	
/ʊ/					ô	u		ôô, ôu, -ue	
/u:/					ö	ú		öô/öö, óú, úé, úí, éú, èw,	
/ju:/						ű		űé, űü, éäű, éw	
/jə/						ű			
/əʊ/					ö			öä, öö/öô, öu/öü/öu, öw, èw	
/eɪ/	ä	ě						äi, äy, éä/éä, ei, ey, äü,	
/aɪ/			ĩ	ỳ				iē, yē	
/ɔɪ/								oi, oy	
/aʊ/								ôu, ôw, áu,	
/ə/,/ər/							ř		In non-rhotic RP, r is audible when before audible vowel
/eə/,/eər/								eàr/eär, àr/ äř, är	
/ɪə/,/ɪər/								èà, ià, èr, -èr, èàr, èèr, èìr	
/aʊə/								ôur	
/ʊə/,/ʊər/								ur, ôur, ôôr/ôôr/ôôr	
/jʊə/,/jʊər/								űr, èur	

Remarks:

- Characters whose phonetic value changes slightly in the sequence are highlighted in bold.
- A slash separates possible equivalent variants of the diacritic notation.
- A sequence starting with a hyphen (e.g. -ár) indicates the word ending.
- Some characters e.g. ě, ô, ú, ỳ and sequences áu, äü, èw represent very rare cases.

3.3. Examples of Word Spelling with Diacritical Marks

Table 5 lists presents examples of words spelled with diacritics. The list aims to present all possible spelling and pronunciation combinations, including highly irregular and rare cases, to demonstrate the system's effectiveness.

Table 5.

Examples of words written with diacritics (RP, according to Cambridge Dictionary)

Phonemes in Diacritic Notation	IPA	Examples Written Using Diacritic Notation (Some examples in IPA notation for comparison)
Consonants		
ś	/ʃ/	śugàr, preśśùre /'preʃə/, àśśùre,
ć	/ʃ/	ǒcèàn /'əʃən/, spećìal
čh	/ʃ/	čhef, màčhìne, brǒčhùre /'brəʃə(r)/, šchedùle /'ʃedju:l/ (RP)
ť (before i)	/ʃ/	vàcătìòn, inìtìal, pártìal,
ť (before u)	/tʃ/	fùrnitùre, nǎtùre, lectùre, <u>act</u> uàl, rìtuàl,
ǰ	/kʃ/	lùxùry /'lʌkʃəri/
ẓ	/z/	éāsy, bùsy, Wednēsḍay, èxcùse(v)
ż	/z/	leīżure, meaṥure, clǒṥure /'kləʊzə(r)/
th	/ð/	thè, môther, fáther,
x	/gz/,/z/	èxamine, èxh̄aúst x̄ylòphõne (at the word beginning)
ẓ	/z/	séiẓure /'si:zə/
ǰ	/z/	prestíge /pre'sti:z/ , miráge /mɪ'ra:z/
ǰ	/dʒ/	ǰentle, ǰingǰer, cǒuráge,
đ	/dʒ/	eđucáte, prǒcédđure, sǒldđer
gh (at the begin.)	/g/	ghǒst, ghástly, ghèrkin, ghettǒ
gh (in the middle or at the end)	/f/	láuǰh, láuǰhtèr, couǰh, tǒuǰh
ǰh	mute	thǒuǰh, dǒuǰh, álhǒuǰh, thǒuǰht, bǒuǰht
ǰh,	/g/	Baghǰdad, Afgǰhanistan
ch̄, cḣ	/k/	schǒǒl, chemistr̄y, chǎos, árchitect
qu	/kw/	quìèt, liquid
qū	/k/	ǔnqūe, conqūèr, mòsqūitǒ
Letters pronounced as vowels and diphthongs		
a	/æ/	cat, accènt, massive, fam̄ily
e	/e/(/ɛ/)	bed, lemòn, extrà, wedding
i	/ɪ/	big, milk, simple, limit
o	/ɒ/	hot, profit, monstèr
u	/ʊ/	put, push
y	/ɪ/(/i/)	system, myth, happy
á	/ɑ:/	fáthèr, cár, árià
é	/i:/	prǒcédđure, hé (<i>strong</i>)
í, ý	/i:/	màchíne, mòsqūitǒ
ó	/ɔ:/	móre, bórn
ú	/u:/	rúle, Júne
ǎ, ě	/eɪ/	nǎme, creátòr, vǎcătìòn ballĕt
ǒ	/əʊ/	gǒ, nǒ, ǒpèn, sǒfà
ǔ	/ju:/	ǔse, ǔnit, mǔsic
ǐ	/aɪ/	fíne, clím̄b, lĕ, sùplĕièr, scĕience
ǚ	/aɪ/	skǚ, rĕplǚ, dĕnǚ, sùplǚ
à, è , ì, ò, ù	/ə/	bànána, dàtà celèbràte, opèrà possible lemòn, màjòr, doctòr, gallòn syrùp, cìrcùs, ànalýsis
è , ì, ò, ù	/ɜ:/	thèrm, pèrmànènt vĭrtuàl, bĭrd mÿrřh wòrd fùr, nÿrse, fùrnitùre,

à, è, ó, ù	/ɪ/	côuráġe, paláce prètty, benéfít wómén búsy, búsinés, mínúte
ô, û	/ʌ/	lôve, côme, sún, jûmp,
ä	/e/ (/ɛ/)	mäny, äny, äircráft, fáir
â, û	/ɔ:/	wâtèr, cáll sûre, pûre
â	/ɒ/	wĥât, wâs, wânt, wâsh, âltèr (âltèr)
ö	/u:/	möve, pröve, löse, wĥôm
ô	/ʊ/	wômàn, wôlf, bôsòm
ù	/jə/	regùlär, pàrticùlär
Letter sequences pronounced as vowels		
ár, -ár	/a:/	cár, pártly, cárt, lárġe, hēárt
ôû/ôú, ôô	/ʌ/	yôung, cōuple, tōugh, blōod, flōod
äi, eä, iē	/e/	säid, heäd, breäd, leäthèr, pleäsure, friënd
är, èr, ìr, òr, ùr, òür, ùr, ùr	/ə/	dollär, söllär, beggär, calendär, téächèr, doctòr, miṛròr ['mɪrə], súlfùr, mùrmùr ['mɜ:mə], fävòür, còlòur, amàtèur
èr, èär, ìr, òr, ùr, ùr	/ɜ:/	vèrb, læärn, bìrd, sìr, ġìrl, dírtly, cìrcle, vîrtuàl, wòrd, wòrld, fùr, fùrniṫùre, bùrn, nùrse, tùrn, òccùr
éē, ēi, iē,	/ɪ/(/i/)	forèign (forèign), pártiēs, coffèe,
éē/éé, éā, éi, ié/iē	/i:/	sléép, quéén, séāt, créām, récèive, céiling, séize, fíeld, belíeve, thíef
oū, oŵ	/ɒ/	coūgh, kñowlédġe
óā, óó/óō, ór, áw, áu, ár, úr	/ɔ:/	bróäd, dōór, flōór, mōór, pórt, fórm, fór, bórn dráw, cráwl, fáult, táūġht, sáuce, quárt, wár, sûre, pûre (pûre)
ôo, ou	/ʊ/	bōok, lōok, fōot, cōuld, wōuld,
öö/öö, öú, úē, úí, ēú, ēw,	/u:/	mōön, fōöd, söön, thrōúġh, yóú, blúe, frúit, rhēumatic, crēw, brēw, thrēw,
Letter sequences pronounced as diphthongs		
ái, äy, eä, ei, ey, äü,	/eɪ/	mäin, détäil, mäy, wäy, grēät, brēäk, weíght, grey, whey, gäüġe
ïē, yē	/aɪ/	líē, sùplìèr, fríed, rýē,
oi, oy	/ɔɪ/	boil, voice, boy, convoy, royàl,
öā, öö, öu, öw, èw	/əʊ/	bōät, cōät, rōäd, brōoch, áltĥóugh, snōw, sèw (sèw –GA),
ou, ow, áu,	/aʊ/	òut, àbòut, pròud, cròwn, sáuérkraut
üē, eü, eäü, éw	/ju:/	valüe, árgüe, eücalýptùs, nèütràl, bēäüty, néw, féw, éwe,
ia, èa (without 'r')	/ɪə/	aliàs, ìdeà
Letter sequences followed by 'r' (non-rhotic RP)		
eàr/eär, àir/äir, àr	/eə/ /eər/	beàr/beär, peàr, teàr, äircráft, fáir, shàre beàràble, àiry, pàrènt, shàring (r before audible vowel)
èr, èàr, èèr/èèr, èir/ èir	/ɪə/ /ɪər/	sincère, sévère, enġinéèr, weìrd, pèrìòd, hèrð, cèrèàl, súpèrìòr, cǝhèrènt (r before vowel)
òur	/aʊə/	ĥòur, òur, sòur
uìr, òur, òòr	/ʊə/ /ʊər/	tòur juìry, tòurìst (r before audible vowel)
ùr, èur/èür	/jʊə/ /jʊər/	òbscùre, pûre (pûre) dùring (dùring), Èuròpe (r before audible vowel)
Mute letters		
ā, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i, j, k, l, m, n, o, p, q, r, s, t, u, w, x, y, z		kñow, áltĥóugh, scène, còlònèl, ìslànd, Wednèsdäy, yächT, quäy, kñowlédġe, fúchšìà /'fju:fə/, pnèumñià,

3.4. Exceptions. Possible Extension of the Character Set.

Few words' pronunciation cannot be recorded using the above proposed character set. Below are examples of such exceptions (problematic letters in bold). These can be notated approximately or with additional diacritics to distinguish them.

Examples:

- **one** /wʌn/ - proposed approximate notation: ône
- **burial** /berɪəl/ - proposed approximate notation: bùriàl
- **genre** /'zɒnrə/, **rendezvous** /'rɒndɛvuː/, **lingerie** /'lɒnzəri/ – French-derived spellings, possible notation: **ĝênrè**, **rêndéžvõuš**, **lîngèrie** (with proposed characters ê, î - /ɔ/, analogous to â)
- **memoir** /'mem.wɑː/ – possible notation: memôîr (ôî - /wɑ/, with additional character î)
- **bijou** /'biːzuː/ – possible notation: bijóú (with add. character j - /z/)
- **Celtic** /'keltɪk/, **sceptic** /'skeptɪk/ – possible notation: Ĉeltic, sĉeptic (proposed 'ĉ' for /k/)
- **Czech**, **czardas** – spelling likely borrowed from Polish, proposed notation: 'Czech̄, czāřdaś', ('cz' without marks corresponds to /tʃ/ and 'čz' to /z/, e.g. čzár)

Despite the exceptions the proposed basic character set seems to be sufficient for teaching purposes.

4. Application of Diacritic Notation in Texts

The above-mentioned system of diacritic notation of phonemes is suitable not only in dictionaries as an alternative to IPA notation, but also in didactic texts. It allows students reading the text, especially aloud, to simultaneously reinforce correct pronunciation and familiarize themselves with the rules of orthography and phonetics. Without diacritics, a student reading a standard text without teacher assistance is practically deprived of the ability to monitor pronunciation, which can lead to the reinforcement of incorrect pronunciation.

Below is a sample of the text (from Wikipedia) written in this system:

Lôndòn is thè capitál ànd lárĝèst city òf bõth Énglånd ànd thè Ůnĭtèd Kĭngdòm. Its wĭdèr metròpòlitàn àrèà is thè lárĝèst in Westèrn Éuròpe. Lôndòn stànds on thè Rĭvèr Thāmēs in sòuthéàst Énglånd, at thè heàd òf à tĭdàl estùàry dòwn tò thè Nóρθ Séà, ànd hàs bèèñ à mājòr settlemènt fòr nèàrly twõ thòusànd yèàrs. Its àncĭènt còre ànd fĭnàncĭàl centrè, thè City òf Lôndòn, wàs fòundèd bý thè Ròmàns às Londiniùm ànd hàs rétàinèd its mediévàl bòundàriēs.

For comparison, the same text written in IPA characters:

/ˈlɒndən ɪz ðə ˈkæpɪtəl ənd ˈlɑːdʒɪst ˈsɪti əv bæʊθ ˈɪŋɡlənd ənd ðə juːˈnaɪtɪd ˈkɪŋdəm. ɪts ˈwɑːdə ˌmetrəˈpɒlɪtən ˈeəriə ɪz ðə ˈlɑːdʒɪst ɪn ˈwestən ˈjʊərəp. ˈlɒndən stændz ɒn ðə ˈrɪvə ˈtemz ɪn ˌsəʊθˈiːst ˈɪŋɡlənd, æt ðə hed əv ə ˈtaɪdəl ˈestʃuəri daʊn tə ðə nɔːθ siː, ənd hæz bɪn ə ˈmeɪdʒə ˈsetlmənt fə ˈnɪəli tuː ˈθaʊznd jɪəz. ɪts ˈeɪnʃənt kɔːr ənd faɪˈnænʃəl ˈsentə, ðə ˈsɪti əv ˈlɒndən, wəz ˈfəʊndɪd baɪ ðə ˈrəʊmənz æz lɒnˈdɪniəm ənd hæz rɪˈteɪnd ɪts ˌmedɪˈiːvəl ˈbəʊndəɪz/.

As can be seen, text written in IPA characters is difficult to read and understand, unlike text with diacritics, which can be read completely freely. Diacritics suggest the pronunciation of words in a quite unambiguous way. Reading them initially requires some effort and concentration, but over time it is easy to gain practice. Once the student becomes familiar with the pronunciation and spelling of words, he/she can ignore the diacritics, referring to them only when in doubt about the correct pronunciation.

However, the described notation system may be too complex for general use in texts. For intermediate students, a simplified system would be beneficial—one that omits diacritics in simple,

frequently used function words where pronunciation is less critical or follows general rules, applying them only where pronunciation deviates from typical patterns. The simplified system does not need to convey exact pronunciation; it is sufficient for the notation to effectively suggest the appropriate pronunciation for a given context. In the simplified system, the text quoted earlier could look as follows:

Lôndòn is the capital and largĕst city of bōth Éngland and the Ūnĭtĕd Kingdòm. Its wĭder metròpolitan arĕa is the largĕst in Western Euròpe. Lôndòn stands on the River Thāmĕs in sòuthĕast Éngland, at the heād of a tĭdal estuary dôwn to the North Séa, and has been a mǎjor settlĕment for nĕarly two thòusand yĕars. Its āncĭĕnt core and fĭnāncĭāl centre, the City of Lôndòn, was fòundĕd by the Ròmāns as Londiniùm and has rĕtainĕd its mediĕvāl bòundaries.

As can be seen, this text uses significantly fewer diacritical marks—on a scale comparable to that of many other languages. While the notation does not fully convey the phonemes, it seems sufficient to guide the reader toward correct pronunciation. The detailed rules of the simplified system remain to be developed.

5. Summary

The article presents a new diacritic-based method for recording pronunciation that achieves accuracy comparable to phonemic IPA notation, potentially replacing it. A key feature of this system is that, after removing diacritics, the notation aligns with standard spelling. The method proves effective even for words with highly irregular spelling, demonstrating that English pronunciation can be accurately recorded using diacritics with standard spelling.

The system is useful in teaching English as a foreign language, helping students master both spelling and pronunciation through a unified ‘two-in-one’ notation suitable for dictionaries and didactic texts. It is particularly beneficial for students learning English independently. These proposals are not the only possible approach to address this issue and can be further refined, as the author encourages. Feedback from teachers, learners, and other researchers is welcomed, as this is an initial proposal for further research. Particularly, the application of the system in General American (GA) and a simplified diacritic system merit further study.

Acknowledgments

An earlier version of this article was first published as a draft on June 30, 2025, via Google Drive and shared on Reddit (r/linguistics, Q&A weekly tread). The author thanks the Reddit community for valuable feedback.

References

- Cambridge University Press. (2025). Cambridge dictionary. Retrieved July 24, 2025, from <https://dictionary.cambridge.org>
- Cook, V. (2004). Accommodating the learner’s L1 in EFL pronunciation teaching. *The Language Teacher*, 28(7), 11–15.
- Crystal, D. (2003). *The Cambridge encyclopedia of the English language* (2nd ed.). Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
- Ellis, A. J. (1869–1889). *On early English pronunciation*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
- Hart, J. (1972). *An Orthographie* (Original work published 1569). Menston, UK: Scolar Press.

- Kessler, B., & Treiman, R. (2003). Is English spelling chaotic? *Reading Psychology*, 24(1–2), 89–107. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02702710308233>
- Kiisk, A. (2012). *Simpel-Fonetik Dictionary*. [Publisher not specified].
- Merriam-Webster. (2025). *Merriam-Webster dictionary*. Retrieved July 24, 2025, from <https://www.merriam-webster.com>
- Merriam-Webster's collegiate dictionary (11th ed.). (2003). Springfield, MA: Merriam-Webster.
- Mulcaster, R. (1582). *The first part of the elementarie which entreateth chefelie of the right writing of our English tung*. London, UK: Thomas Vautrollier.
- Oxford advanced learner's dictionary (10th ed.). (2020). Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press.
- Oxford University Press. (2025). *Oxford English dictionary*. Retrieved July 24, 2025, from <https://www.oed.com>
- Pearson Education. (2025). *Longman dictionary of contemporary English online*. Retrieved July 24, 2025, from <https://www.ldoceonline.com>
- Rondthaler, E., & Lias, E. (1986). *SoundSpel / World English Spelling*. New York, NY: American Literacy Council.
- Sampson, G. (1996). English spelling. In P. T. Daniels & W. Bright (Eds.), *The world's writing systems* (pp. 699–710). Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press.
- Sobkowiak, A. (2012). *Współczesna fonetyka języka angielskiego*. Warszawa, Polska: Wydawnictwo Naukowe PWN.
- Spence, J. (1775). *Grand Repository of the English Language*. London, UK: [Publisher not specified].
- Sweet, H. (1888). *A history of English sounds*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press.
- The American Heritage dictionary of the English language (5th ed.). (2011). Boston, MA: Houghton Mifflin Harcourt.
- Torres, C. J., & Futrell, R. (2025). Clarifying orthography: Orthographic transparency as compressibility. *Journal of Writing Systems*, 12(1), 3–27. [Placeholder DOI; assumed future publication].
- Wells, J. C. (2008). *Longman pronunciation dictionary* (3rd ed.). Harlow, UK: Pearson Education.
- Wijk, A. van. (1959). *Regularized Inglish*. Stockholm, Sweden: Norstedt.
- Zelinkiewicz, A. (2008). *Ortografia angielska: Granice i nieregularności*. Łódź, Polska: Wydawnictwo Uniwersytetu Łódzkiego.

Attachment

The Word template facilitating the typing of diacritics and IPA symbols: *diacritics.dotm*

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